

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

**Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education
Program among South-West, Colleges of Education in Nigeria**

DAVID, Seyi (PhD)¹
david.seyi@lcu.edu.ng

&

SODAMOLA, Seun Olaiwola²
elderdj2002@gmail.com
08023998945

¹Department of Arts & Social Science Education, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State,
Nigeria

²Department of Office Technology & Management Education, Federal College of Education
(Technical), Akoka, Lagos

Abstract

The aim of the study is to investigate Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education Program among South-West, Colleges of Education in Nigeria. It is pertinent to consider all possible factors that impact on the lecturer's performance. After home, school is the most important place and lecturers are the stakeholders for students to learn and develop their educational competencies. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The sample covered total number of (1105) one thousand one hundred and five 200 level Business Education program during 2024/2025 academic session in south west Colleges of Education. A structured questionnaire on Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education Program was used to gather data and information needed. The validity of the instrument was determined by two experts which were Business Education lecturers while the internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained for the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics: mean, standard deviation and ANOVA were used to analyze data. Findings revealed that, there is strong positive and high academic achievements in business education program with mean scores range from 3.39 to 3.68, and the relatively low standard deviations (between 0.526 and 0.719) and status of lecturers' factors in Business Education program is high with average weighted mean of (X3.36) with standard deviation of (0.66). It was concluded that, high level of academic achievement in Business Education Program exists among students as a result of lecturers' factor and application of appropriate teaching methods. It was recommended that; motivation is a mechanism through which the lecturers can produce good results by delivering the quality education to Business Education students.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Business Education Program, Lecturers' Factors, Teaching, Skills

Introduction

The performance of lecturers in any academic task has always been of special interest to the government, educators, parents and society at large. There is a growing demand from the government and the public for lecturer accountability. Lecturers celebrate and are rewarded when their schools and teaching program are highly ranked. Lecturers are rewarded collectively when they work in institutions which are identified as high-performing citadel of learning. Lecturers who excel in their teaching business program are rewarded during school appraisal time. While appreciating the value of rewarding lecturers who produce better results, lecturers should also not escape a portion of blame when students perform poorly. It has been proven that lecturers have an important influence on students' academic achievement. They play a crucial role in educational attainment because the lecturer is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action and principles based on practice during interaction with the students. (Gilbet, 2017).

The definition of the concept of Business Education has evolved over time. This is evident in the different definitions offered by various authors and researchers in trying to make clear the meaning of business education. Business Education as a course that prepares students for entry in advancement of jobs within business; and prepares them to handle their own business affairs to function intelligently as consumers and citizens in a business economy. Similarly, Business Education encompasses knowledge, attitudes, and skills needed by all citizens in order to effectively manage their personal businesses and economic system.

Statement of the Research Problem

Also, it seems lecturers are having low performance due to the inadequate motivational factor. Lecturers in Nigeria have expressed a lot of dissatisfaction about the lack of human resource development, poor working conditions, poor remuneration and poor human relations that exist in schools as these impact on the students' academic achievement in Business Education Program. Hence, it appears that major problem inherent in the teaching and learning processes is as a result of lecturer-factor.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education Program among South-West, Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify level of students' academic achievement in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria.
2. Examine status of lecturers' factors (lecturers' Salary, working conditions, teaching experience and teaching facilities in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria).

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

Research Questions

The below research question guided the study:

1. What is the level of students' academic achievement in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria?
2. What is the status of lecturers' factors (lecturers' Salary, working conditions, teaching experience) and teaching facilities in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Student's academic achievement is a dynamic phenomenon as there are a number of different factors that affect a student's achievement. Such effect of each of these factors varies from student to student and context to context. Therefore, the research on measuring impact of various factors on student performance is challenging to generalize. One Specific factor that has received attention from is the lecturer's attitude towards the student at hand. Lee (2020) argued that a student's motivation, attitude towards school, their willingness to do homework and confidence in their learning behavior are all a factor of the lecturer's attitude of teaching towards the students. These instrumental factors collect together to shape a students' personality over time, therefore, argue the authors, that lecturer's attitude has long lasting impact on the student achievement, well beyond his or her academic career. In their research, the authors have strongly recommended lecturers to offer support to their students in their learning, and for this, they have advised lecturers to create an environment of positive expectations.

In every department of the Business Education in a tertiary institution, there is the need for them to work in furtherance of the National Policy of Education directive as well as, making sure that, its objectives relate to the NPE offers in view of the certificates and degree options in the Business Education programme. The National Commission for Colleges of Education provides Nigeria Certificate in Education with latest Minimum Standard which stipulates four (4) areas of specialization for Business Education which are:

- a. Accounting Education Option
- b. Entrepreneurship Option
- c. Marketing Education Option
- d. Office Technology Education Option

Lecturers' Gender

There is a significant relationship between and students' academic achievement. Gender refers to socially constructed differences between [male and female](#). Scholars, policymakers, and practitioners have observed and seem to agree upon socially constructed differences between male and female and its significant effects in their lives. Studies conducted across

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

the world among the students studying in different levels found a significant [gender difference](#) in academic performance. Several studies have reported that female lecturers outperform their male counterparts while others have objection for this. (Maccoby, 2019).

Lecturers' Experience

Lecturers' experience has been the prime predictor of students' academic achievement. Lecturers' teaching experience is significantly related to students' achievement. Another study concluded that lecturer management of classwork, assignments given to students have an impact on student achievement especially when it is well explained, motivational, corrected and reviewed during class time and used as an occasion for feedback to students.

Educational Qualifications

Lecturers play a pivotal role in providing education to the students. After home, the school is the most important place for students to learn and develop their educational and social competencies. Every institution strives to recruit good and qualified teaching staff that can deliver quality education to its students. Only highly qualified and committed teaching staff or lecturers can produce effective results by producing good quality of students, who contribute to their country in future. Therefore, it is crucial for schools to keep the talented or key teaching staff. Because only qualified lecturers can give best education to the students. Thus, for the quality of education the qualifications of lecturers matter a lot.

Lecturer's Income

Okike (2022) was of the opinion that, there is increasing concern about the performance of students and the quality of the lecturers in our nation's schools. Higher lecturer pay (linked to accountability) has been put forward as one of the ways of attracting and retaining high-quality lecturers, but direct evidence of whether higher lecturer pay results in improved student achievements has been sparse. There is linkage between lecturer pay and lecturer quality. The relationship between lecturer pay and lecturer quality appears to be different depending on the time period being considered. In the short-run, pay increases do not appear to have noticeable effects on the quality of lecturers entering teaching. Over the long-run, trends in relative lecturer pay seem to be related to trends in lecturer quality offer a different explanation for the decline in aptitude of those choosing teaching as a profession, attributing it largely to the pay compression brought about by unionization.

Teaching Environment

Typically, the teaching process impacts students learning through the lecturers adopted pedagogy approach; the classroom environment created; that is, lecturers accommodating

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

attitude towards students. Ideally, the class environment should on the one hand ensure students of actual teaching being carried out, while on the other, it should ascertain lecturers of actual learning occurring. Moreover, the learning curve is amplified when a student thinks more like a lecturer, and the lecturer, a student. It was argued that, deepening a students' advanced thought pattern through environment paves the way for improved classroom performance, thereby encouraging them to bring forth innovative and differing ideas that come with their unique knowledge and skills set (Nilson, 2022).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey helps the researcher to employ a mixed-methods research approach that combines quantitative analysis and qualitative insights to gather existing data, insights, and models. (Lopez, 2022). The population of the study comprised (1105) one thousand one hundred and five 200 level Business Education students in all the Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria. The research used the entire population as the sample since the total population under study was not too much to work with. Hence, total number of (1105) one thousand one hundred and five 200 level Business Education students from all Colleges of Education from the South-West States in Nigeria served as sample population. A total of one thousand, one hundred and five (1,105) copies of the questionnaire were administered, out of which, one thousand and one (1001) copies were successfully retrieved, accounting for 90.6% of the total, while from the retrieved questionnaires, nine hundred and nine (909) copies were deemed useful for the analysis, accounting for 82.3% of the total. The research instrument was structured question. The validity of the instrument was determined by two experts which are Business Education lecturers. The Internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained for the study. The instrument was administered through the help of research assistants and collected back after the completion. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of academic achievement in Business Education Program in in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Academic Achievement in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD
1	Students do perform excellently in business education program due to lecturers' competency and available facilities for students to	636 (70)	225 (28.1)	14 (1.5)	4 (0.4)	3.68	.526

www.ziystemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

2	practice with. Students attain practical skills that enhance their academic achievement in their courses apart from knowledge on computer literacy.	455 (50.10)	426 (46.9)	24 (2.6)	4 (0.4)	3.47	.573
3	The interest that students put in the theoretical and practical courses improves their level of academic achievement.	503 (55.3)	323 (35.5)	63 (6.9)	20 (2.2)	3.44	.719
4	One of the most important features of vocational skill in business education programme is its orientation towards academics achievement and self-employment.	442 (48.6)	415 (45.7)	43 (4.7)	9 (1.0)	3.42	.631
5	Every student has important influence on their academic achievement through practical session in business education program.	422 (46.4)	436 (48.0)	39 (4.3)	12 (1.3)	3.39	.636

Average Weighted Mean = 3.48 General Decision = High

Source: Field Work 2025

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree and STD = Standard Deviation

Threshold: 0-1.49 = very low; 1.50-2.49 = Low; 2.50-3.49 = High and 3.50 and above Very High.

Table 1 presents a summary of responses to various statements about students' academic achievements in business education program. The responses are categorized into four levels: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Also, the mean and standard deviation (Std. D) for each item provide insights into the central tendency and variation of responses. For item 1: "Students do perform excellently in business education program due to lecturers' competency and available facilities for students to practice with." The vast majority (98.1%) of students agree that their excellent performance in business education program is due to the competence of their lecturers and the availability of facilities. The high mean (3.68) indicates strong agreement with the statement, while the low standard deviation (0.526) suggests that most students share similar views, with little variation. For item 2, "Students attain practical skills that enhance their academic achievement in their courses apart from knowledge on computer literacy." Nearly all students (97%) agree that practical skills gained from keyboarding enhance their academic performance beyond just basic computer literacy. With a mean of 3.47, the

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodamola, S. O. 2025)

responses show a strong agreement, and the standard deviation (0.573) indicates that most students' responses are consistent, with slight variability.

For item 3, "The interest that students put in theoretical and practical courses improves their level of academic achievement." The majority (90.8%) of students believe that their interest in theoretical and practical courses helps improve their academic performance. The mean of 3.44 suggests general agreement, though the slightly higher standard deviation (0.719) reflects more variability in opinions, indicating that some students are less certain about the impact of interest on their academic success. Item 4: "One of the most important features of vocational skill in business education program is its orientation towards academic achievement and self-employment." About 94.3% of students agree that computer keyboarding skills contribute to both academic success and self-employment opportunities. The mean of 3.42 indicates strong agreement, while the standard deviation (0.631) shows some variation in responses, though the overall consensus is positive. For Item 5: "Every student has important influence on their academic achievement through practical sessions in business education program." A significant majority (94.4%) of students feel that practical sessions help them control their academic performance. The mean score of 3.39 shows that students generally agree with this statement, and the moderate standard deviation (0.636) suggests that while most students agree, there is some variability in their responses.

Generally, across all items, most students (90% or more) either strongly agree or agree with the statements, showing strong positive and high academic achievements in business education program. The mean scores range from 3.39 to 3.68, which indicates that the students largely agree with each statement. The relatively low standard deviations (between 0.526 and 0.719) suggest that the responses are clustered around the mean, meaning there is general consistency in students' views, though there is slightly more variation in responses to items related to personal interest and practical influence on achievements.

Research Question 2: What is the status of lecturers' factors (motivation, lecturers' Salary, working conditions, teaching experience in Business Education Program in in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Lecturers' Factors (Lecturers' Salary, Working Conditions, Teaching Experience) in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD
1	Lecturer's factors are indispensable elements in the teaching and learning process; as it improves students' academic	398 (43.8)	443 (48.7)	54 (5.9)	14 (1.5)	3.35	.668

www.ziستمfugusau.com.ng
 des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

	achievements in Business Education program.						
2	Lecturer's factors make them a good facilitators, architects, managers and engineers of teaching pedagogy to improve students' academic achievement in Business Program.	414 (45.5)	413 (45.4)	66 (7.3)	16 (1.8)	3.35	.691
3	Effective teaching and learning coupled with adequate classroom management that stir up expected academic achievements in Business Education program is a product of lecturers' factors.	434 (47.7)	411 (45.2)	51 (5.6)	13 (1.4)	3.39	.661
4	Lecturers' factors determine the quality of instructional delivery, when it comes to implementation of the curriculum; educational policies and attainment of better academic achievement in Business Education program.	434 (47.7)	403 (44.3)	51 (5.6)	21 (2.3)	3.38	.697

Average Weighted Mean = 3.36

General Decision = High

Source: Field Work 2025

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree and STD = Standard Deviation

Threshold: 0-1.49 = very low; 1.50-2.49 = Low; 2.50-3.49 = High and 3.50 and above Very High.

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics on lecturers' factors (motivation, salary, working conditions, teaching experience) and their perceived influence on students' academic achievements in Business Education program skills at Colleges of Education in South West Nigeria. These statistics reflect the collective opinions of the respondents based on the items. For item 1, "Lecturer's factors are indispensable elements in the teaching and learning process; as it improves students' academic achievements in Business Education program". The data shows that a significant majority of respondents either strongly agree (43.8%) or agree (48.7%) that lecturers' factors are crucial in improving students' academic achievements in Business Education program. Only a small portion disagreed (5.9%) or strongly disagreed (1.5%). The mean = 3.35, which indicates that, on average, respondents agree with the statement and the standard deviation (Std. D) = 0.668 suggests moderate variability in responses, showing consistency in agreement among respondents.

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

For item 2, “Lecturer’s factors make them a good facilitators, architects, managers and engineers of teaching pedagogy to improve students’ academic achievement in Business Education program”. Similarly, most respondents strongly agree (45.5%) or agree (45.4%) that lecturers’ factors help them become facilitators, managers, and engineers in teaching pedagogy for Business Education program. A smaller percentage disagreed (7.3%) or strongly disagreed (1.8%). The mean = 3.35, suggesting that the majority of respondents support this view. Std. D. = 0.691, which indicates slightly more variability compared to Item 1, but still suggests overall agreement. For item 3, effective teaching and learning coupled with adequate classroom management that stir up expected academic achievements in Business Education program is a product of lecturers’ factors. The majority of respondents strongly agree (47.7%) or agree (45.2%) that effective teaching and classroom management are products of lecturers’ factors. Disagreement was very low, with only 5.6% disagreeing and 1.4% strongly disagreeing. The mean = 3.39, showing a high level of agreement. Std. D. = 0.661, indicating relatively low variability, meaning responses were quite consistent. For item 4, respondents largely believe that lecturers' factors influence instructional delivery quality, educational policies, and students' academic achievements. Most respondents either strongly agree (47.7%) or agree (44.3%), while only a small portion disagreed (5.6%) or strongly disagreed (2.3%). The mean = 3.38, indicating a high degree of agreement among respondents. Std. D. = 0.697, showing a moderate level of variation in responses, though still within a reasonable range.

Overall, across all the items, the respondents overwhelmingly agree that lecturers' factors- such as motivation, salary, working conditions, and teaching experience- play a vital role in enhancing students' skills in Business Education program in Colleges of Education in South West Nigeria. The mean scores for all items are consistently high (ranging between 3.35 and 3.39), demonstrating that most respondents have a positive view of lecturers' influence on academic achievements in Business Education program. The standard deviations (ranging between 0.661 and 0.697) show that while there is some variability in responses, most participants generally agree with the statements. These results emphasize the importance of supporting lecturers in various aspects, including improving their working conditions and compensation, to enhance educational achievements in Business Education program and related program.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one aimed at identifying the level of academic achievement in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria. Findings revealed that academic achievement in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria is high. This can be attributed to several interrelated factors. Firstly, the quality of the curriculum plays a crucial role; these institutions have implemented a well-structured program that emphasizes essential computer skills, ensuring students receive

www.zistemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodamola, S. O. 2025)

comprehensive training in keyboarding. Access to resources is another significant factor. If colleges provide modern computers, relevant software, and ample learning materials, students are more likely to practice and develop their keyboarding skills effectively. Additionally, the presence of qualified lecturers cannot be overstated. Experienced and skilled lecturers who employ effective teaching methodologies can greatly enhance students' learning experiences, leading to improved achievements. The finding is supported by several studies, suggesting positive achievements associated with effective keyboard instruction. For instance, a study found that students using interactive computer software achieved notable proficiency in typing, enhancing their keyboard skills and academic achievements.

The second research question aimed at examining the status of lecturers' factors (lecturers' Salary, working conditions, and teaching experience) in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria. It was discovered that the status of lecturers' factors (lecturers' Salary, working conditions, and teaching experience) in Business Education Program in Colleges of Education in South West, Nigeria is high. This suggests that several key elements are positively influencing lecturers' effectiveness in teaching these skills. First, salary that lecturers receive can significantly impact their job satisfaction and performance. A competitive salary can provide financial security, which allows lecturers to focus more on their teaching responsibilities rather than worrying about their financial situations. This, in turn, can lead to better engagement in the classroom and a commitment to student success. The working conditions within the Colleges also play a vital role. Supportive environments that offer access to necessary resources, such as computers and teaching aids, along with reasonable workloads, can foster a more effective teaching atmosphere. When lecturers have the right tools and a conducive environment, they are better positioned to deliver high-quality instruction in Business Education Program. Teaching experience is another influential factor. Experienced lecturers often possess a wealth of knowledge and practical skills that can enhance their teaching effectiveness. They are typically more adapt at addressing diverse learning needs and implementing effective teaching methods. Their experience can also provide them with insights into the best practices for Business Education Program, leading to improved student achievements. Supporting this view, a study concluded that fair compensation and a conducive work environment, or the drive to serve society through education, is a significant factor influencing lecturer performance and are key drivers of lecturer performance in higher education institutions.

Conclusion

In the wake of development/evaluation in business education, the future of Business Education in Nigeria is considered promising and calls for government and other

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

stakeholders to show commitment to the agenda. The conduct of development process in Business Education should be based on specific criteria that constitute the major factors which should be considered in conjunction with an educational evaluation. Hence, lecturers' factors should be given serious attention. Business educators therefore, should see curriculum development as a continuous process which should be conducted on a regular basis because continuous evaluation provides basis for adjusting programmes to meet the manpower needs of the country. Hence, it provides the best means of quality control for our programmes (Mac, 2020). This review/paper has made large and outstanding contribution 'to the knowledge and practice in the field of business education. However, a few new contributions are worthy of mention. First, by identifying the perspectives of stakeholders and curriculum gaps that exist between them, the perceptions of the stakeholders can be understood clearly. By understanding the nature of the perspectives, business curriculum developers/designers are more informed of the expectations of the stakeholders and the process of curriculum development/design to satisfy the needs and requirements of the stakeholders is made easier and more effective. If curriculum development process is properly addressed with positive approach, business educators will be in a better position to critically analyze and determine how effective education changes are to be handled.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Colleges of Education should focus on enhancing lecturers' factors and this can be achieved by ensuring that lecturers are well-supported through competitive compensation, conducive working conditions, and professional development opportunities.
2. Since students in Colleges of Education in South West Nigeria are doing well in business education program, schools should offer more advanced classes or workshops to help them build on this skill.
3. Since the factors influencing lecturers' effectiveness in teaching business program are strong, Colleges of Education should continue to support and enhance these motivating conditions.

References

Adeyemo, B.E (2018). *Principle of Education and Practice of Education*. Ado Ekiti: Standard Press and Bookshop C. (Nig.) Limited.

www.zijstemfugusau.com.ng
des@fugusau.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15675043>

(Influence of Lecturers' Factors on Academic Achievement in Business Education ... David, S. & Sodomola, S. O. 2025)

Aitkin, A.B. (2019). *Teacher Leadership and Behaviour Management*. London: Paul Chapman Publishing, 14-37

Asikkhia, D. C (2019). *Influence of Motivation-Monetary Rewards on Job Performance. A survey of Organization Performance and Human Capital Management*. New York: Guilford Press.

Bankole, A. G. (2020). *A Textbook on Teachers' Factor influencing Teaching of Business Subjects. State*. Nathadex Publishers. Ilorin, Kwara:

Gilbet, A.A. (2017). Computer Assisted Learning: Perceptions and Knowledge Skills of Undergraduate. *Science and Education Journal*, 5 (45), 103-121

Kalu, V. (2018). A Study on Adjustment, Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement and Job Stress of Private Secondary School Teachers. *Indian Journal of Research*, 4(1), 78-80.

Kuperminc, G. (2019). School Social Climate and Individual Differences in Vulnerability to Psychopathology among Middle School Students. *Journal of School Psychology*, 39(2), 141-159.

Lee E.J. (2028). Social Achievement Goals and Social Adjustment in Adolescence: A Multiple-Goal Perspective. *The Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 60 (3), 79-84.

Lopez, C. (2022). Peer Victimization and Rejection: Investigation of An Integral Model of Effects on Emotional, Behavioural and Academic Adjustment in Early Adolescence. *Journal of Clinical Child and Adolescent Psychology*, 3(1), 25-36.

Mac B, L. (2020). The Perceived Competence Scale for Children. *Child Development*, 53(2), 87-97.

Maccoby, E. E. (2019). Middle School Improvement and Reform: Development and Validation of a School- Level Assessment of Climate, Cultural pluralism and school safety. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(3), 567-568.

Morgan, O.E. (2021). Teaching and Learning through Problem Solving. *Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics*, 5(4), 50-55

Nilson, E.O. (2022). Teaching at Its Best: A Research-Based Resource for College Instructors. *Science and Education Journal*, 5(45), 201, 103-12.

Okike, V.N. (2022). ICT Initiatives in Teacher Education. *University News*, 43(18), 103-104.